

Nicotinoyl Dipeptides and Their Derivatives as Possible Tuberculostats

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Nicotinoyl-(±)-methionyl-(±)-methionine, nicotinoyl-(±)-methionylglycine, and a number of their derivatives have been synthesised and screened for *in vitro* antitubercular activity. Out of 24 compounds tested, 4 have been found to inhibit the growth of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (H₃₇R_v) at 1:10,000 dilution.

Amino-acids like D-(−)-isoleucine¹, aspartic acid, β-alanine, glycine, methylglycine², and (+)-lysine³ have been shown to inhibit the growth of various microorganisms. Hydrazides⁴ of (±)-alanine, (−)-leucine, (±)-serine, (±)-methionine, and (±)-phenylalanine inhibit the growth of tubercle bacillus. Among a few peptide analogues prepared by Dunn *et al.*⁵, glycyl β-2-(thienyl)-alanine was the most active against microorganisms. A number of tri- and tetra-peptide derivatives like glycylglycyl-β-2 (thienyl)-alanine and glycyl-(−)-leucylglycyl-(−)-leucine were found to inhibit the growth of *Escherichia coli*. Antibiotics related to amino-acids and polypeptides are known: Penicillin⁶, Azaserine⁷, Cycloserine⁸, Gramicidin S⁹, and Tyrocidine B¹⁰ are some of the examples.

Some derivatives of amino-acid conjugates of pyridine carboxylic acids¹¹, synthesised in this laboratory, have been shown to be active *in vitro* against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H₃₇R_v.

In the present communication the synthesis of nicotinoyl-(±)-methionyl-(±)-methionine (IIIa), nicotinoyl-(±)-methionylglycine (IIIb), and their derivatives are described. All the compounds have been screened for antitubercular activity *in vitro* against *M. tuberculosis* H₃₇R_v.

The ethyl esters (IIa and IIb) of the nicotinoyl dipeptides were prepared by condensing nicotinoyl-(±)-methionine (I: R' = -CH₂CH₂SCH₃) with ethyl esters of (±)-methionine and glycine respectively, using dicyclohexylcarbodi-imide¹² (DCC) as the condensing agent.

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3. Jeney, *ibid.*, 1949, **43**, 9145g.
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CHART I

IIa, IIIa, IVa: R'-R'' = -CH₂CH₂SCH₃. IIb, IIIb, IVb: R' = -CH₂CH₂SCH₃; R'' = -H. V-XIII: R' = R'' = -CH₂CH₂SCH₃; R''' = aldehyde residue as shown in Table I. XIV-XX: R' = -CH₂CH₂SCH₃; R'' = -H; R''' = aldehyde residue as shown in Table I. XXI: R' = R'' = -CH₂CH₂SCH₃. XXII: R'-R'' = -H.

Good yields were obtained when the condensation was carried out at low temperatures (-5°). Nicotinoyl-($\pm$)-methionine was prepared by two methods, viz., (a) via acid chloride¹⁴ and (b) via acid azide¹⁵; the overall yields were better in the latter case. DCC was prepared starting from cyclohexylamine¹³. The esters (IIa) and (IIb) were then converted into the hydrazides (IVa and IVb) which with aldehydes afforded the substituted hydrazines (V-XX). Treatment of nicotinoyl dipeptide hydrazides with isonicotinoyl chloride furnished the corresponding acyl derivatives (XXI, XXII). The general scheme of the reactions is indicated in Chart I.

EXPERIMENTAL

Nicotinoyl-($\pm$)-methionine (I: $R' = -CH_2CH_2SCH_3$): (a). *Through Acid Chloride*.—Nicotinoyl chloride was prepared by refluxing potassium nicotinate (5 g.) in benzene (25 ml) with thionyl chloride (10 ml) for 2 hr. and then removing the excess of thionyl chloride under reduced pressure. The residue was taken in benzene (100 ml) and ($\pm$)-methionine ethyl ester (4.5 g.) in dry benzene (10 ml) was added slowly under stirring. After stirring for 12 hr., water (100 ml) was added and the solution made alkaline with sodium bicarbonate solution. Benzene portion was separated, washed free of alkali, and on removal of the solvent, nicotinoyl-($\pm$)-methionine ethyl ester obtained was crystallised from ether-light petroleum; yield 4.89 g. (56%), m.p. $67-68^{\circ}$.

The ester (1 g.) was suspended in *N*-KOH solution (25 ml) and stirred for 6 hr. The unchanged ester was extracted with ether and the aqueous part acidified (Congo red) with HCl (dil.). On concentration and cooling, nicotinoyl-($\pm$)-methionine crystallised out; yield; 0.6 g. (66.6%), m.p. $213-14^{\circ}$ (lit.¹¹ m.p. $213-14^{\circ}$).

(b). *Through Acid Azide*.—Nicotinoyl-($\pm$) methionine was obtained by stirring ($\pm$)-methionine (14.9 g.) in 1*N*-NaOH solution (100 ml) with nicotinic acid azide¹⁶ (15.0 g.) at the room temperature. The solution was kept alkaline throughout by adding NaOH solution from time to time. After allowing it to stand overnight, the solution was evaporated to dryness, the residue dissolved in a small amount of water, and acidified with 2*N*-HCl to pH 3.5. Nicotinoyl-($\pm$)-methionine separating was crystallised from water; yield 17.78 g. (70%), m.p. $213-14^{\circ}$.

Nicotinoyl-($\pm$)-methionyl-($\pm$)-methionine Ethyl Ester (IIa).—The acid (I) (2.54 g.), dissolved in dry dimethylformamide (30 ml), was added under constant stirring to ($\pm$)-methionine ethyl ester (1.77 g.) and dicyclohexylcarbodi-imide¹² (2.06 g.) in dimethylformamide (20 ml), the flask being cooled with ice-salt freezing mixture. The reaction mixture was kept in the cold room at about -5° for 48 hr. and then the unchanged DCC was decomposed with a few drops of glacial acetic acid. The precipitated dicyclohexylurea was filtered and the filtrate evaporated to dryness. The residue was taken in ethyl acetate and the insoluble material was removed by filtration. The filtrate was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and water, dried, concentrated, and light petroleum was added to precipitate the product which was crystallised from ethyl acetate-light petroleum; yield

13. Chancel, *Compt. rend.*, 1893, **116**, 330; Schmidt *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1938, **71**, 1933.

14. Meyer and Graf, *Biochem. Z.*, 1930, **229**, 154; Kametani and Iida, *Chem. Abs.*, 1952, **46**, 8119^c.

15. Curtius, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1895, **52**, 243.

16. Rohrlieh, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1951, **284**, 6.

2.90 g. (70.4%), m.p. 112°. (Found: C, 52.08; H, 6.81; N, 10.03. $C_{18}H_{27}O_4N_3S_2$ requires C, 52.30; H, 6.54; N, 10.16%.)

Nicotinoyl-(±)-methionyl-(±)-methionine (IIIa).—The above ester (1g.) was stirred with 1*N*-KOH solution (3.5ml) for 6 hr. and then filtered; the filtrate was acidified with 1*N*-HCl to pH 3.5. The product obtained was crystallised from aqueous ethanol (90%); yield 0.69 g. (71.4%), m.p. 148°. (Found: N, 10.12. $C_{16}H_{23}O_4N_3S_2$ requires N, 10.65%.)

Nicotinoyl-(±)-methionyl-(±)-methionine Hydrazide (IVa).—The ester (IIa) (4.13 g.) in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed with 60% hydrazine hydrate (2 g.) for 4-6 hr. Ethanol and excess of hydrazine hydrate were removed under reduced pressure and the residue was crystallised from aqueous ethanol (95%); yield 3.02 g. (75.6%), m.p. 158°. (Found: C, 48.23; H, 5.97; N, 17.59. $C_{16}H_{25}O_3N_3S_2$ requires C, 48.11; H, 6.27; N, 17.54%.)

Condensation of Aldehydes (nine) with (IVa): *General Procedure*.—Equimolecular quantities of the hydrazide (IVa) and the aldehyde were refluxed in anhydrous ethanol for 6 hr. On concentration and cooling, the product (V-XIII) crystallised. It was recrystallised from a suitable solvent (Table I).

[The aldehydes employed for making the compounds (V-XIII) were: piperonal, *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde, quinoline-2-aldehyde, *m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde, cinnamaldehyde, benzaldehyde, *p*-methoxybenzaldehyde, *p*-aminobenzaldehyde, *o*-hydroxybenzaldehyde].

Nicotinoyl-(±)-methionylglycine Ethyl Ester (IIb).—The acid (I) (2.54 g.), dissolved in dry dimethylformamide (30 ml), was added to glycine ethyl ester¹⁶ (1.03 g) and DCC (2.06 g.) in dimethylformamide (20 ml) at -5°. The product was isolated as in the case of (IIa): yield 2.48 g. (73.2%), m.p. 101°. (Found: C, 52.83; H, 5.81; N, 12.31. $C_{15}H_{21}O_4N_3S$ requires C, 53.08; H, 6.24; N, 12.38%.)

Nicotinoyl-(±)-methionylglycine (IIIb).—The ester (IIb) (1 g.) was stirred with 1*N*-KOH solution (3.25 ml) for 6 hr., filtered, and then acidified with 1*N*-HCl to pH 3.5 and kept at -5° for a few hours. The acid separating was crystallised from aqueous ethanol (95%); yield 0.72 g. (81.08%), m.p. 190.5°. (Found: N, 13.21. $C_{13}H_{17}O_4N_3S$ requires N, 13.50%.)

Nicotinoyl-(±)-methionylglycine Hydrazide (IVb).—The ester (IIb) (3.39 g.) in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed with 60% hydrazine hydrate (2.0g.) for 6 hr. Ethanol and excess of hydrazine hydrate were removed under reduced pressure and the residue crystallised from ethanol; yield 2.46 g. (75.7%), m.p. 170-71°. (Found: N, 21.28. $C_{15}H_{19}O_3N_3S$ requires N, 21.52%.)

Condensation of Aldehydes (seven) with (IVb): *General Procedure*.—Equimolecular quantities of (IVb) and the aldehyde were refluxed in anhydrous ethanol for 6 hr. The product (XIII-XX) crystallised on concentration and cooling. It was further recrystallised from a suitable solvent (Table I). (All the aldehydes except benzaldehyde and *p*-aminobenzaldehyde used previously were condensed here.)

INH (Isonicotinic Acid Hydrazide): Acyl Derivatives of Nicotinoyl Dipeptide Hydrazides (XXI & XXII): *General Procedure*.—Compounds (XXI-XXII) were prepared by taking the corresponding nicotinoyl dipeptide hydrazide in a small amount of dry pyridine and adding an equimolar amount of isonicotinoyl chloride in dry pyridine slowly under

stirring. Excess of pyridine was removed under reduced pressure and water added. The precipitate obtained was crystallised from aqueous ethanol (85%). Yields were generally poor.

Compound (XXI): m.p. 165. (Found: N, 16.24. $C_{22}H_{28}O_4N_6S_2$ requires N, 16.66%).

Compound (XXII): m. p. 285° (decomp.). (Found: N, 23.15. $C_{16}H_{16}O_4N_6$ requires , 23.60%).

TABLE I

Aldehyde condensation products of nicotionyl dipeptide hydrazides.

R''' =	R' = R'' = $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{SCH}_3$;			R' = $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{SCH}_3$; R'' = $-\text{H}$.				
(Aldehyde residue).	Compound No.	M. P.	% Nitrogen Found.	% Nitrogen Req'd.	Compound No.	M.P.	% Nitrogen Found.	% Nitrogen Req'd.
$(3,4\text{-O-CH}_2\text{-O})\text{C}_6\text{H}_3-$	V	203-204°	13.23	13.18	XIV	215°	15.73	15.32
$4\text{-(CH}_3)_2\text{NC}_6\text{H}_4-$	VI	204-205°	16.01	15.85	XV	219°	18.34	18.42
$2\text{-C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N}-$	VII	228.5°	15.18	15.62	XVI	184°	18.42	18.10
$3\text{-OH-C}_6\text{H}_4-$	VIII	237-38°	13.93	13.92	XVII	181°	16.63	16.30
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}=\text{CH}-$	IX	213°	14.10	13.65	XVIII	196°	16.29	15.93
C_6H_5-	X	235-36°	14.57	14.37	..	..	..	..
$4\text{-CH}_3\text{O-C}_6\text{H}_4-$	XI	184-85°	13.63	13.54	XIX	169°	16.00	15.79
$4\text{-NH}_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4-$	XII	213-14°	16.29	16.73	..	..	..	..
$2\text{-OH-C}_6\text{H}_4-$	XIII	195°	13.71	13.92	XX	203°	16.44	16.30

*Pharmacology**

The antitubercular activities of these compounds were tested by the surface culture technique using the virulent human strain, *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, H_{37}R_v with ethylene glycol as the solvent; serial dilutions of the drug were prepared in Youmans media and sterilized at 15 lbs. pressure for 20 min. A thin film of the *M. tuberculosis* H_{37}R_v , taken from a 12 to 14-day culture of the organism by a 4-mm loop, was gently floated on to the surface of the drug dilutions. The tubes were paraffin-sealed and incubated at 37°. Suitable solvent controls were run at the same time. The extent of surface growth was recorded at weekly intervals. The results as seen at the end of 3 weeks are indicated.

Out of the 24 derivatives prepared and tested, 1-nicotinoyl-(±)-methionyl-(±)-methionyl-2-*p*-aminobenzylidenehydrazine (XII), 1-nicotinoyl-(±)-methionyl-(±)-methionyl-2-*o*-hydroxybenzylidenehydrazine (XIII), 1-nicotinoyl-(±)-methionylglycine ethyl

*Pharmacology part of this investigation was carried out by M. Sirai.

ester (IIb) and *N'*-isonicotinoyl-*N''*- [N-nicotinoyl-(±)-methionyl-(±)-methionyl]-hydrazine (XXI) inhibit the growth of *M. tuberculosis* H₃₇R_v at 1:10,000 dilution. 1-Nicotinoyl-(±)-methionyl-(±)-methionyl-2-*m*-hydroxybenzylidenehydrazine partially inhibits the growth of the organism at 1:10,000 dilution.

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